

Plain English summary (long form)

Why did we do this study?

Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) are related disorders whereby young people, most commonly around the age of seven, suddenly experience several physical and psychiatric symptoms. PANS and PANDAS may persist for years, usually getting much worse at certain points during the year. The symptoms of PANS/PANDAS can be extremely severe and have a huge impact on families.

The amount of research about PANS and PANDAS has been increasing since the conditions were first named in the late 1990s, but there is a lack of consensus about almost all aspects of the conditions. This uncertainty covers the causes and diagnosis of the conditions, how to treat them, and what it is like to live with PANS or PANDAS. This lack of agreement makes it difficult to decide where future research should be focused. It also means that patients, families and suspected patients experience additional challenges beyond those presented by having the conditions.

We conducted an 'Evidence and gap map' (EGM) which is a way of collecting and organising all published evidence about PANS/PANDAS and presenting it in one place via an interactive display. By doing this, anyone using the EGM could find out how much research has been done on any aspect of the conditions, and where there are gaps in the evidence.

The EGM was therefore intended to provide a clear overview of research on PANS/PANDAS. Its purpose was to:

- 1) Allow people with an interest in PANS/PANDAS to see all the research on the topic, and easily find studies
- 2) Make it easy to see where new studies are needed to improve our understanding of PANS/PANDAS
- 3) Help plan future reviews of the evidence, which can provide greater consensus about the different areas of the field (causes, diagnosis, treatment, experiences etc)

What did we do?

We aimed to find every study about PANS/PANDAS that collected some data. To do this, we searched comprehensively and included any type of study, except for letters, opinion pieces, editorials and literature reviews (that weren't 'systematic'). We also searched relevant websites, looked for studies that were in progress or about to be published, and included presentations from conferences. All included studies focused on people with a diagnosis of PANS or PANDAS.

Once we screened out all the irrelevant studies, we went through them all to categorise what they were about. This meant that, once they were in the EGM, they could be found by their key characteristics – for example, map users could search specifically for studies about diagnosis, or those that talk about sleep difficulties as a symptom. We coded dozens of characteristics to make the EGM detailed.

After coding the features of each study, we produced the EGM and made it available online.

Throughout this project, the team of reviewers worked closely with clinical experts, a senior representative of the PANS PANDAS UK charity, young people with the conditions, and parents of young people with the conditions.

What did we find?

We included 445 individual pieces of research in the EGM, of which 338 were full studies and 107 were conference presentations. About half of the studies came from the USA, and there was very little from the UK. A lot of the research was of lower scientific rigour, coming from case studies that describe one patient, or a small number of patients, at a time. This type of evidence is not very useful for patients or healthcare providers. The rate at which evidence has been produced has increased a lot in the last 10 years, but there are still large gaps in the understanding of PANS/PANDAS.

It is evident that much more research is needed on PANS/PANDAS, however by producing the EGM it is now easier to see where this evidence is needed most. Some key findings were:

- 1) There is scope for evidence reviews in almost every area of research, which could help update and solidify understanding in the field.

- 2) New studies are needed in every area, but perhaps most urgently about the causes and clinical features of the conditions. Without this, all other areas of understanding are held back, particularly diagnosis and treatment.
- 3) The treatments tended to focus on tackling the infection that triggered symptoms, or treating symptoms directly. However these were mostly case studies, and there was very little evidence to support these approaches in patients with PANS/PANDAS. There is enough evidence to conduct a new review of these treatments to help inform clinical practice.
- 4) Studies reporting on the experiences of PANS/PANDAS have emerged in the last ten years, and they should be combined in a review, so that we can develop a clearer understanding of what patients, families and clinicians have experienced.

In summary

Overall, there are a lot of studies about PANS and PANDAS, but the vast majority are of low rigour and offer little value when seeking to understand the conditions, or advance knowledge about diagnosis or treatment. However, the recent surge in evidence offers some promise, and at least an increased level of attention. By collating the evidence and presenting it in an EGM, we have provided a valuable resource that will allow patients, carers and clinicians to access research, and help plan for future studies.